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The Influence of Training Methods and Students Work Ethos on Work Competency

Eny Lunarny¹, Wachidi², Alexon³, Johannes Sapri⁴

¹ Doctoral Program, Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia. Email: eny.lunarny12@gmail.com

² Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia. Email: wachidi@unib.ac.id

³ Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia. Email: alexon@unib.ac.id

⁴ Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia. Email: johannessapri@unib.ac.id

Correspondence: Eny Lunarny, Dotoral Program, Universitas Bengkulu, Indonesia.
Email: eny.lunarny12@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of training methods and work ethic on students' work competencies. The focus of teaching implementation is observed using two training methods, namely: on the job training method using internship training and *simulasi* method using simulation. The initial work ethic of students is limited to low and high categories. This type of research is a quasi-experimental with a 2×2 factorial design. The research population is all students of class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK Negeri 7 Bengkulu City, totaling 123 people. The sample was selected using the intact group technique from four classes selected to be two learning classes as the experimental group. The selected class is drawn by lottery to determine the treatment of the internship training and *simulasi* methods. Each treatment group was grouped based on low work ethic and high work ethic. The research instrument is a work competency assessment sheet and student work ethic. The data analysis technique used is 2-way analysis of variance. The results of the study can be concluded that: (1) the average work competence of students using the internship training method is higher than those using the simulation method. (2) The average work competence of students who have a high work ethic is higher than students with a low work ethic. (3) There is an interaction effect between training methods and work ethic on the work competence of students. (4) Students with a high work ethic who take part in the internship training method have higher work competencies compared to the simulation method. (5) Students with a low work ethic who take part in the internship training method have lower work competencies than those using the simulation method.

Keywords: Internship Training, *Simulasi*, Work Ethic, Work Competence.

1. Introduction

Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state (Act). -Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003). The atmosphere and learning process is realized through education, consisting of formal,

non-formal, and informal education that complement and enrich each other. Formal education levels consist of basic education, secondary education, and higher education. Secondary education consists of general secondary education and vocational secondary education (SMK).

Vocational secondary education is secondary education that prepares students especially to work in certain fields. This is in line with the opinion of Budiyo (2008) which explains that vocational education is secondary education that prepares students to become workers and independent in certain fields. Vocational education is based on 3 (three) central philosophies, namely: (1) the reality of the competencies taught in vocational education is the same as in the business and industrial world (DUDI), (2) the truth of vocational education in schools is the same as in the business and industrial world, and (3) the value of Vocational Education in schools is the same as in the business and industrial world. Vocational education must provide experience to work effectively and efficiently, have psychomotor knowledge and skills and always keep abreast of world technology developments in the world of work.

The main problem in learning at SMKN 7 Bengkulu City consists of two things. First, the implementation of learning strategies carried out in schools does not condition the real problems that occur in the industrial world. Second, the learning strategies applied generally do not pay attention to learning needs based on the level of work ethic in students. The needs in question are the need for appropriate learning strategies and the need for job training.

Based on these two things, an effort or learning innovation strategy is needed, one of which is the application of job training through the internship training method. The advantages of internship training are believed to be able to overcome these problems, by conditioning learning in accordance with the industrial world, where students not only get real learning skills and experiences but also intellectually, emotionally and physically to be actively involved in real situations, able to think critically and able to deal with problem solving in environmental situations where students are trained to work by actively constructing their own knowledge in remembering, understanding, observing, applying and analyzing the phenomena encountered during internship training.

This internship training method sharpens the implementation of theory and practice specifically for students who receive formal education at school as a preparation stage to work in industry under the supervision of a supervisor and teacher who is competent in their field, with the implementation of a short period of time and block of time with paying attention to the psychology of students so that the internship training method is not boring for students in supporting the achievement of their work competencies.

Teachers in the learning process need to pay attention to the level of student work ethic so that teachers can make appropriate learning strategies in an effort to increase work competence. A high work ethic is needed in the world of hospitality, for that students are expected to have high discipline, be honest, diligent, responsible, able to work together and work hard.

The work ethic of students is built from motivation, because motivation is the driving force that moves someone to do something to achieve goals, this will be seen from the ethics and work perspective that is believed and realized through concrete determination and behavior in the world of work, because concrete behavior is implemented in the world of work reflects the work ethic of students who are based on work ethics and perspectives that have been believed so far. Work ethic in the world of work implies two important things, namely how a person behaves towards his work and how he does his job. For this reason, strong motivation and determination in realizing the moral values of the right work culture are very important, because generally students are motivated to behave in accordance with the moral standards of their group, simultaneously with the development of character, competence and performance so that motivation and work passion and work behavior grow. consistent in students.

Then, another supporting factor that can improve the competence of students through the job training is the role of the presenter (instructor) in delivering the material, motivating and facilitating students. The material presenter (instructor) as the spearhead in delivering material and training directly to students has a big

responsibility in motivating students to take part in the training. Starting from the description above, it is necessary to carry out further studies through research entitled the influence of the internship training method and work ethic on the work competence of students at SMKN 7 Bengkulu City. The study was conducted to test several theories in obtaining findings, including: (1) whether there are differences in work competencies between students who follow the internship training method and students who follow the simulation method, (2) whether there are differences in work competencies between students who have low and high initial work ethic, (3) is there an interaction effect between the internship training method and work ethic on the work competence of students, (4) is there a difference in the work competence of students who have a high work ethic between students who follow the internship training method and students who follow the simulation method, (5) whether there are differences in the work competencies of students who have a low work ethic between students who follow the internship training method and the simulation method.

2. Method

The research method used was a quasi-experimental design with a 2×2 factorial. The treatment variable in this study was a training method consisting of two treatments, namely: the internship training method and the simulation method. The dependent variable in this study is the work competence of students. While the attribute variable is the work ethic of students which includes a high work ethic and a low work ethic. The population in this study was class XI students in the hospitality department at SMK Negeri7 Bengkulu City, totaling 123 students. The steps of the sampling technique in this study are as follows: First, conduct an intact group selection to determine the treatment class. In this first stage, two classes were selected from the four existing classes, namely: XI PH1, XI PH2, XI PH3, and XI PH4. The four classes are not too much different in ability.

The results of the sample selection through the intact group (randomized group) were selected for two classes, namely class XI PH1 and class XI PH3 with 30 students each. Groups were selected based on the class where the researcher did not form a new group. Second, from the two selected classes, a draw was made to select the experimental class and the control class. From the results of the draw, Class XI PH2 was obtained as an experimental class using the internship training method. Then, Class XI PH1 as a control class (simulation method). Third, the third stage is to classify the level of work ethic. The value of work ethic in the form of secondary data taken from homeroom and counseling guidance teachers (BK) in each treatment group.

The work ethic value of each treatment group was grouped based on the category of high work ethic and low work ethic. The grouping based on the ranking of the work ethic values obtained from the BK teachers by taking the 50% who got the highest score were grouped in the high work ethic. Furthermore, 50% of the lowest grades of students are grouped with low work ethic. So that obtained 15 categories of low work ethic and 15 categories of high work ethic in each treatment class. The data analysis technique in this study used univariate statistical testing with the analysis of variance test (Anava).

3. Results and Discussion

The results of data analysis in this study based on each hypothesis testing can be concluded as follows. First, there are differences in work competencies between students who follow the internship training method and students who follow the simulation method in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. The more effective method of influencing work competence is internship training with an effect of 65.59%. The ANOVA test results show that there is a significant difference where the significance value of the test results is $0.000 \leq \text{sig} : 0.05$. Second, there are differences in work competencies between students who have a low and high initial work ethic in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. The group that has the highest influence on competence is the high work ethic group with an influence of 94.00%. The ANOVA test results have a significant difference where the significance value of the test results is $0.017 \leq \text{sig} : 0.05$. Third, there is an interaction effect between the internship training method and work ethic on the competence of students in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. This is indicated by the results of the ANOVA test with a significance value of $0.010 \leq \text{sig} :$

0.05. The influence given between the training method and work ethic is 78.10% where the value of R2 on the output of the test results is 0.781.

Fourth, there are differences in the work competencies of students who have a high work ethic between students who follow the internship training method and students who follow the simulation method in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. The average work competence in the high work ethic group who participated in the internship training was higher than the simulation method group. The results of the analysis of the average competency scores showed that the high work ethic group who followed the internship training method had an average of 78.80 while the simulation method group got an average score of 71.57. ANOVA test results obtained a significance value of $0.00 < 0.05$. This means that statistically there is a significant difference between the work competencies of students who have a high initial work ethic and the treatment of the internship training method and the simulation method.

Fifth, there are differences in the work competencies of students who have a low work ethic between students who follow the internship training method and the simulation method in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. The average work competence in the low work ethic group who participated in the internship training was higher than the group with the simulation method. The results of the analysis of the average competency value showed that the group with low work ethic who followed the internship training method had an average of 84.10 while the simulation method group obtained an average value of 73.14. ANOVA test results obtained a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that there is a statistically significant difference between the work competencies of students who have a low initial work ethic and the treatment of internship training and simulation methods.

4. Conclusion

Based on processing, data analysis, hypothesis testing, and discussion of research findings, it can be concluded as follows. 1) There is a difference in work competence between students who follow the internship training method and students who follow the simulation method in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. A more effective method of influencing competence is the internship training method. 2) There is a difference in work competence between students who have a low and high initial work ethic in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. The group that has the highest influence on work competence is the high work ethic group. 3) There is an interaction effect between the internship training method and work ethic on the work competence of students in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. 4) There are differences in the work competencies of students who have a high work ethic between students who follow the internship training method and students who follow the simulation method in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. The average work competence in the high work ethic group who participated in the internship training was higher than the simulation group. 5) There are differences in the work competencies of students who have low work ethic between students who follow the internship training method and the simulation method in class XI of the Hospitality Accommodation Department at SMK N 7 Bengkulu City. The average work competence in the low work ethic group who followed the simulation method was higher than the internship training group.

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